

CVA under Settlement Currency Risk: Stablecoin-Denominated Atomic Settlement

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Abstract

Background. Tokenized securities markets and DLT-based atomic settlement are expanding rapidly, yet existing CVA theory assumes the settlement currency is risk-free. **Problem.** When stablecoins serve as the settlement currency, their depeg risk creates an unpriced risk dimension that standard CVA frameworks do not capture. **Method.** We propose the *Settlement Currency Valuation Adjustment* (SCVA), a new adjustment term inspired by, but distinct from, the Collateral Cost Adjustment (CCA) of [Fujii and Takahashi \(2013\)](#). Using a two-state continuous-time Markov chain (a pure jump process) for the depeg state and a Hull–White-style parametric exposure proxy, we derive a semi-analytical SCVA expression. **Results.** Under USDC 2023 parameters, SCVA exceeds the settlement-period CVA reduction by a factor of approximately 2.1. A 100,000-path Monte Carlo simulation reproduces the closed-form expression within 0.32% relative error. Cross-stablecoin analysis reveals that a Japanese Type II Fund Transfer Business stablecoin with trust-based 101% bankruptcy-remote custody achieves near-zero SCVA, whereas offshore stablecoins and prepaid-type tokens (which lack par redemption rights) consistently exceed the breakeven threshold $\delta \cdot \lambda_{PD} \approx 0.0113$. **Implications.** The economic value of atomic settlement depends critically on the regulatory design of the settlement currency—specifically, whether par redemption backed by legally bankruptcy-remote trust assets is guaranteed.

Keywords: CVA, SCVA, stablecoin, depeg risk, atomic settlement, DLT, tokenized securities

JEL Classification: G13, G15, G21, G28

1 Introduction

The rapid growth of tokenized securities¹ and stablecoin-based payment infrastructure is reshaping the landscape of securities settlement. Distributed ledger technology (DLT) enables *atomic settlement*—the simultaneous, instantaneous exchange of securities and payment—eliminating the settlement period that traditionally exposes counterparties to credit risk during T+2 settlement.

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¹Industry practice, particularly in the Japanese STO market, often uses the synonymous term *security tokens* (). We follow the academic-regulatory convention of *tokenized securities* throughout.

This reduction in counterparty exposure is widely cited as a key benefit of DLT-based settlement (Bank for International Settlements, 2023). More broadly, Duffie and Zhu (2011) showed that changes in clearing and settlement infrastructure can significantly affect counterparty risk, though their analysis focused on central clearing rather than DLT.

However, when the payment leg of atomic settlement uses stablecoins rather than risk-free fiat currency, a new risk dimension emerges. Stablecoins are crypto-assets designed to maintain a 1:1 peg to a fiat currency (Gorton and Zhang, 2023), but this peg can temporarily break due to issuer credit events or reserve asset impairments. The March 2023 USDC depeg event, triggered by the collapse of Silicon Valley Bank, saw USDC trade at a 12% discount to the dollar for approximately three days. Lyons and Viswanath-Natraj (2023) provide an empirical analysis of the mechanisms that normally keep stablecoins pegged, highlighting the role of arbitrage design in stabilization. The systemic nature of such events—where banking stress simultaneously triggers depeg and elevates counterparty default risk—makes this a particularly relevant concern for CVA practitioners.

The standard CVA framework (Brigo et al., 2013) implicitly assumes that settlement currency is risk-free. Fujii and Takahashi (2013) extended CVA theory to handle asymmetric and imperfect collateralization, decomposing the portfolio value into a clean price, bilateral CVA, and a Collateral Cost Adjustment (CCA) that is independent of credit risk. Importantly, even in their framework, the collateral/settlement currency itself is assumed to be risk-free—subject to interest rate differentials across currencies (Fujii and Takahashi, 2011), but not to value impairment. Piterbarg (2010) similarly treats funding costs without considering settlement currency risk.

This paper addresses the gap by introducing the **Settlement Currency Valuation Adjustment (SCVA)**, a new adjustment term that captures the cost of depeg risk in stablecoin-denominated settlement. Inspired by, but distinct from, Fujii–Takahashi’s CCA, SCVA shares the additive decomposition structure but addresses a fundamentally different risk dimension: the value impairment of the settlement currency itself, rather than funding cost differentials between risk-free currencies. We derive a semi-analytical expression for SCVA using a two-state Markov depeg model and demonstrate that, under USDC 2023 parameters, SCVA exceeds the settlement-period CVA reduction by a factor of approximately 2.1.

1.1 Literature Positioning

This work sits at the intersection of three literatures.

(1) CVA, collateral, and funding adjustments. Piterbarg (2010) and Brigo et al. (2013) established the integrated CVA/FVA/Collateral framework for derivative pricing under counterparty risk. Fujii and Takahashi (2013) formulated derivative pricing under asymmetric and imperfect collateralization within an FBSDE framework, deriving CCA as an additive credit-risk-independent adjustment. We extend this lineage by focusing on **settlement-currency** (rather than collateral-currency) imperfection.

(2) Stablecoin economics and depeg risk. Lyons and Viswanath-Natraj (2023) empirically analyze the stability mechanisms of major stablecoins, identifying reserve quality and redemption design as decisive. Gorton and Zhang (2023) draw the analogy to historical “wildcat banking” to argue that unregulated stablecoins replicate that systemic fragility. These literatures characterize

the mechanics of depeg but do not address **counterparty risk valuation** for obligations denominated in stablecoins.

(3) DLT settlement and counterparty risk reduction. Duffie and Zhu (2011), Auer et al. (2022), and Bank for International Settlements (2023) discuss DvP and wholesale-CBDC settlement architectures and the benefits of compressing the settlement window. This paper bridges these strands by quantifying how the atomic-settlement benefit depends on the choice of settlement currency.

Relationship to Quanto CVA. SCVA is superficially related to quanto CVA (Brigo et al., 2011, 2014), which adjusts for the case where the default-time payoff is denominated in a currency different from the valuation currency. However, SCVA differs in three essential respects: (i) price dynamics are driven by discrete state transitions (not continuous FX volatility); (ii) stablecoins possess a peg-restoration mechanism via primary-market redemption that has no counterpart in continuous FX; (iii) regulatory design directly determines the magnitude of SCVA, introducing an institutional dimension absent from quanto frameworks.

2 Model

2.1 Interest Rate Model and Expected Exposure

We adopt the Hull–White one-factor short-rate model under the risk-neutral measure,

$$dr_t = \kappa(\theta(t) - r_t) dt + \sigma_r dW_t^r, \quad (1)$$

where $\theta(t)$ is calibrated to the initial JGB yield curve. The expected positive exposure $EE(t)$ for the numerical examples is taken as a parametric proxy approximating the typical payer-swap EE shape under Hull–White (Brigo et al., 2013, Ch. 10):

$$EE(t) = EE_0 \cdot \sqrt{t} \cdot e^{-\alpha t}, \quad t \in [0, T]. \quad (2)$$

The \sqrt{t} term reflects the cumulative diffusion variance of the short rate, while $e^{-\alpha t}$ captures the decay of remaining cash flows toward maturity. We use $EE_0 = 100$ and $\alpha = 0.15$ as baseline values (with EE_0 normalized to a unit notional). The main qualitative conclusions (Δ CVA sign and SCVA/settlement-reduction ratio) are robust to the specific shape of $EE(t)$, since both CVA_{conv} and SCVA share the same $EE(t)q(t)$ weight, so proportional shape changes cancel. All parameters are specified in Appendix A.

2.2 Stablecoin Depeg Model

We model the stablecoin peg ratio S_t as a two-state continuous-time Markov chain—a **pure jump process** driven entirely by state transitions:

- **State P (Pegged):** $S_t = 1$
- **State D (Depegged):** $S_t = 1 - \delta$, where $\delta \in (0, 1)$ is the loss-given-depeg

with generator matrix

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} -\lambda_{PD} & \lambda_{PD} \\ \lambda_{DP} & -\lambda_{DP} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where λ_{PD} is the depeg intensity and λ_{DP} is the recovery rate.² Setting $\Lambda = \lambda_{PD} + \lambda_{DP}$, the probability of being in state D at time t , starting from state P, is

$$\pi_D(t) = \frac{\lambda_{PD}}{\Lambda}(1 - e^{-\Lambda t}), \quad (4)$$

and the expected peg ratio is

$$\mathbb{E}[S_t] = 1 - \delta \cdot \frac{\lambda_{PD}}{\Lambda}(1 - e^{-\Lambda t}). \quad (5)$$

2.3 CVA Formulation: The Separation Approach

We considered three candidate formulations for incorporating depeg risk into CVA. To motivate our choice, consider the loss at default time τ : the counterparty owes $EE(\tau)$ in real terms, but recovery of $R \cdot EE(\tau)$ is denominated in stablecoins with real value $R \cdot EE(\tau) \cdot S_\tau$. The loss is therefore

$$L(\tau) = EE(\tau) - R \cdot EE(\tau) \cdot S_\tau = EE(\tau)(1 - R \cdot S_\tau). \quad (6)$$

Expanding $(1 - R \cdot S_\tau) = (1 - R) + R(1 - S_\tau)$ and taking expectations, we obtain the following decomposition. We make two simplifying assumptions: (i) the exposure profile $EE(t)$ and the peg state S_t are stochastically independent, and (ii) the conditional distribution of S_τ given default at time τ equals its unconditional distribution ($\mathbb{E}[S_\tau | \text{default at } \tau] = \mathbb{E}[S_\tau]$). Assumption (ii) rules out wrong-way risk between depeg and default, a simplification whose limitations are highlighted by [Fujii and Takahashi \(2012\)](#), who showed that default dependence leaves an irremovable trace in CDS pricing even under perfect collateralization; we discuss its relaxation in Section 4. We also omit the discount factor $B(0, t)$ for notational simplicity, which is equivalent to working under a forward measure or assuming that discounting effects are second-order over the relevant horizon.

Definition 1 (SCVA). *For a portfolio settled atomically in stablecoins, the total CVA decomposes as*

$$CVA_C = \underbrace{(1 - R) \int_0^T EE(t) q(t) dt}_{CVA_{\text{conv}}} + \underbrace{R \int_0^T EE(t)(1 - \mathbb{E}[S_t]) q(t) dt}_{SCVA}, \quad (7)$$

where $q(t) = h e^{-ht}$ is the default density under a constant hazard rate h .³

Why the SCVA coefficient is R . We make explicit the contractual structure that yields R (not $(1 - R)$) in front of SCVA. Let $EE(t)$ denote the fiat-denominated expected exposure. Upon default, the creditor is entitled to a coin quantity corresponding to the contractual face value $R \cdot EE(t)$; the realized fiat value at the recovery instant is $R \cdot EE(t) \cdot S_t$. The key assumption is

² $\lambda_{DP} = 365/d_{\text{recovery}}$ where d_{recovery} is the mean recovery time in days. For USDC 2023/03 ($d_{\text{recovery}} \approx 3$ days), $\lambda_{DP} \approx 122/\text{year}$.

³More generally, $q(t) = h(t) \cdot \exp(-\int_0^t h(s) ds)$ for time-varying hazard rates. We assume constant h for tractability.

that *the contractual delivery obligation is denominated in the coin quantity*, which is fixed at face value and *not* re-marked at the prevailing S_t .⁴ The loss decomposes as

$$EE(t) - R \cdot EE(t) \cdot S_t = \underbrace{(1 - R) EE(t)}_{\text{default-loss component}} + \underbrace{R EE(t) (1 - S_t)}_{\text{depeg-on-recovery component}} .$$

The first term is the standard CVA loss; the second is SCVA. Intuitively, **the unrecovered portion $(1 - R)$ is never paid and is therefore immune to depeg, whereas the recovered portion R is delivered in coins and bears depeg exposure.**⁵ The decomposition in Eq. (7) follows on taking expectations and integrating against $q(t)$.

We note that SCVA captures the depeg-on-recovery cost of *any* stablecoin-denominated obligation, not only atomically settled ones. The atomicity of settlement is relevant only for eliminating CVA_{settle} (the T+2 settlement-period component in Scenario A); SCVA itself would arise equally in a T+2 stablecoin-denominated settlement.

Relationship to Fujii–Takahashi’s CCA. The additive structure of Eq. (7) is inspired by the decomposition of Fujii and Takahashi (2013), who showed that portfolio value can be written as $V_t = \bar{V}_t + CCA_t + CVA_t$ (their Eq. 3.11), where CCA is independent of credit risk. SCVA shares this additive, credit-risk-independent structure, but addresses a fundamentally different risk: CCA arises from *funding cost differentials* between risk-free collateral currencies, while SCVA arises from the *value impairment* of the settlement currency itself. The analogy is conceptual; a rigorous derivation of SCVA within the FBSDE framework of Fujii and Takahashi (2013) is left for future work.

Why SCVA belongs within the CVA framework. Depeg risk in isolation is a market risk, outside the scope of CVA. However, SCVA specifically captures the *joint* scenario of counterparty default and settlement currency depeg: the recovery cash flows are denominated in stablecoins, and their real value is impaired if the stablecoin is simultaneously depegged. In the absence of default, depeg risk is borne as a market risk by the stablecoin holder and is outside CVA scope.

2.4 Semi-Analytical Approximation

Substituting Eq. (5) into the SCVA definition:

$$SCVA = R \cdot \delta \cdot \frac{\lambda_{PD}}{\Lambda} \int_0^T EE(t) (1 - e^{-\Lambda t}) q(t) dt. \quad (8)$$

Proposition 1. *SCVA is monotonically increasing in λ_{PD} , δ , and R .*

Proof sketch. Write $SCVA = R \delta g(\lambda_{PD}, \lambda_{DP}) \int_0^T EE(t) (1 - e^{-\Lambda t}) q(t) dt$ with $g = \lambda_{PD}/\Lambda$. Monotonicity in δ and R is immediate. For λ_{PD} , $\partial g / \partial \lambda_{PD} = \lambda_{DP} / \Lambda^2 > 0$ and $\partial(1 - e^{-\Lambda t}) / \partial \lambda_{PD} = t e^{-\Lambda t} > 0$, so both factors are non-decreasing. \square \square

⁴Under the alternative specification $S_t^{\text{pay}} = S_t$ (quantity adjusted at the payment-time market price), the recovery value reduces to $R \cdot EE(t) \cdot S_t / S_t = R \cdot EE(t)$ and depeg risk vanishes. Hence the very existence of SCVA depends on the structure that contractual obligations are denominated in coin *quantity*, generating a wedge between contractual face value and realized real value. This wedge is what distinguishes SCVA from a pure FX risk and justifies placing it within the CVA-adjacent framework.

⁵Treating $EE(t)$ as a stablecoin-denominated nominal yields a coefficient of $(1 - R)$ instead and inflates SCVA by roughly 1.5 \times . The qualitative conclusion that SCVA can exceed the settlement-period reduction is unchanged under either specification.

The CVA differential between Scenario C (T+0, stablecoin) and Scenario A (T+2, risk-free) simplifies to:

$$\Delta\text{CVA} = \text{SCVA} - \text{CVA}_{\text{settle}}, \quad (9)$$

where $\text{CVA}_{\text{settle}}$ is the settlement-period CVA component eliminated by atomic settlement. When $\text{SCVA} > \text{CVA}_{\text{settle}}$, the depeg cost exceeds the settlement benefit and $\Delta\text{CVA} > 0$.

3 Numerical Examples

3.1 Calibration

We calibrate the depeg model to the USDC depeg event of March 10–13, 2023. Table 1 summarizes the baseline parameters. All parameters are derived from public data; details are in Appendix A.

For λ_{PD} , we estimate 0.20/year based on one major depeg event in approximately 5 years of USDC operation. Given the extreme sparsity of this sample, we report the exact Poisson 95% confidence interval: $\lambda_{PD} \in [0.005, 1.114]$ /year. Since SCVA is monotonically increasing in λ_{PD} (Proposition 1), the SCVA confidence interval is obtained by direct monotone propagation: $[\text{SCVA}(\lambda_{PD}^{\text{lo}}), \text{SCVA}(\lambda_{PD}^{\text{hi}})]$. The sensitivity analysis in Section 3.4 covers this entire range.

Table 1: Baseline parameter values.

Parameter	Value	95% CI	Source
δ (depeg severity)	0.12 (12%)	—	USDC 2023/03 max depeg
λ_{PD} (depeg intensity)	0.20 /year	[0.005, 1.114]	Poisson estimate ($n = 1, T = 5\text{yr}$)
λ_{DP} (recovery rate)	122.0 /year	—	3-day recovery (365/3)
h (hazard rate)	0.01 /year	—	Investment-grade
R (recovery rate)	0.40	—	Basel standard
T (horizon)	10 years	—	Bond portfolio
Settlement (Scenario A)	2 days	—	T+2 standard

3.2 Results

Table 2 presents the CVA decomposition under baseline parameters.

Table 2: CVA decomposition under USDC 2023 baseline parameters.

Component	Scenario A	Scenario C	Difference
CVA_{conv}	5.3024	5.3024	0.0000
Settlement period	0.000329	0	-0.000329
SCVA	0	0.000694	+0.000694
$\text{CVA}_{\text{total}}$	5.3027	5.3031	+0.000365

The SCVA of 0.000694 is **approximately 2.1 times** the settlement-period CVA reduction of 0.000329. The net ΔCVA is positive: stablecoin-denominated atomic settlement *increases* total CVA relative to T+2 risk-free settlement under USDC parameters. We note, however, that λ_{PD} is highly uncertain; at the lower bound of its 95% CI ($\lambda_{PD} = 0.005$), the ratio drops to nearly zero (atomic settlement wins), while at the upper bound ($\lambda_{PD} = 1.114$), it rises substantially.

Monte Carlo validation. We verify the analytical SCVA formula by simulating 100,000 paths of the two-state Markov chain at daily time steps (Figure 1). The Monte Carlo estimate agrees with the analytical value to within **0.32%** relative error ($\approx 10^{-5}$ absolute), confirming the correctness of the closed-form expression. The reproducible implementation is provided in the supplementary notebook `03_scva_robustness.ipynb`.

Figure 1: Monte Carlo convergence to analytical SCVA. Relative error falls below 1% at approximately 5,000 paths.

3.3 Cross-Stablecoin Robustness

To assess robustness, we calibrate the depeg model to multiple stablecoins with distinct risk profiles and regulatory regimes (Table 3). Parameters for USDC, USDT, and DAI are estimated from publicly documented depeg events.⁶ Parameters for JPYC are assumptions based on the structural properties of each legal form.⁷

Table 3: SCVA across stablecoins by regulatory regime.

Stablecoin	Regulation	δ	λ_{PD}	SCVA (Ratio)	Source
JPYC Type II FTB*	JP regulated, trust 101% bk-remote	1%	0.02	0.000002 (0.0 \times)	Assumed [†]
USDT	Offshore	5%	0.33	0.000319 (1.0 \times)	Observed
USDC	Offshore	12%	0.20	0.000694 (2.1 \times)	Observed
DAI	DeFi (USDC-coll.)	15%	0.20	0.000868 (2.6 \times)	Observed [‡]
JPYC Prepaid	JP prepaid (no redemption)	3%	1.00	0.001433 (4.4 \times)	Assumed [†]

*Trust-based scenario as required for Type II FTB issuers under the revised Japanese Payment Services Act.

[†]Structural assumption; see text for calibration rationale.

[‡]DAI depeg driven by USDC collateral; not independent of USDC.

⁶USDT: 5% depeg during UST/Luna contagion, May 2022, due to market-wide redemption pressure. DAI: 15% depeg during the SVB crisis, March 2023, driven by DAI’s partial USDC collateral backing.

⁷JPYC Prepaid: no redemption right, traded on DeFi markets where thin liquidity causes frequent price deviations. $\lambda_{PD} = 1.0/\text{year}$ is assumed based on observable DeFi price volatility, not formally calibrated. JPYC is currently registered as a Type II Fund Transfer Business (with a 1M JPY per-transaction limit). Reserves are backed by approximately 80% JGBs and 20% bank deposits, with a self-custody wallet model. The “JPYC Type II FTB” row represents a *hypothetical* scenario where the current Type II license is combined with full bank custody—the parameters illustrate how a well-regulated, bank-custodied stablecoin *would* perform in the SCVA framework, not the current JPYC product. $\delta = 1\%$ represents a conservative upper bound on operational redemption friction; $\lambda_{PD} = 0.02/\text{year}$ corresponds to a 50-year mean time between depeg events, comparable to the historical frequency of Japanese commercial bank failures (4 events during the 1997–1998 crisis, none among major banks in the 27 years since). These parameters are illustrative and not calibrated to observed JPYC depeg events, of which none have occurred.

Offshore and DeFi stablecoins (USDC, DAI, JPYC Prepaid) produce SCVA exceeding the settlement-period benefit; USDT is roughly at breakeven (1.0×) (Figure 2). The same issuer (JPYC) shows dramatically different SCVA depending on its legal form: the prepaid-type token (no redemption right, traded on DeFi markets) exhibits SCVA 4.4× the settlement reduction, while the Type II Fund Transfer Business form (trust-based 101% bankruptcy-remote custody, par redemption guaranteed under Article 43 of the revised Payment Services Act) yields SCVA near zero. This contrast underscores that **the regulatory design of the stablecoin determines whether atomic settlement yields a net CVA benefit.**

Figure 2: SCVA across stablecoins. JPYC Type II FTB (hypothetical bank-custody scenario) achieves near-zero SCVA.

For institutions conducting frequent stablecoin-settled transactions, the portfolio-level impact is material. Figure 3 illustrates the annual cumulative SCVA versus settlement-period benefit for varying transaction volumes (assuming 100M JPY notional per trade, USDC parameters).

Figure 3: Portfolio-level annual SCVA (red) versus settlement-period benefit (green). The SCVA cost consistently exceeds the settlement benefit across all transaction volumes.

3.4 Sensitivity Analysis and Breakeven

Figure 4 displays SCVA as a function of λ_{PD} and δ , with the breakeven surface where SCVA equals the settlement-period reduction.

Figure 4: SCVA heatmap. The blue dashed line marks the breakeven where SCVA equals the settlement-period CVA reduction.

Under the approximation $\lambda_{DP} \gg \lambda_{PD}$, the breakeven condition simplifies to:

$$\delta \cdot \lambda_{PD} \approx 0.0113, \quad (10)$$

a hyperbola in the (λ_{PD}, δ) -plane (Figure 5). All offshore/DeFi calibration points (USDC, USDT, DAI, JPYC Prepaid) sit above this curve; only the Type II FTB scenario falls well below.

Figure 5: Breakeven condition with stablecoin calibration points. All offshore/DeFi stablecoins lie above the breakeven curve; JPYC Type II FTB (green star) falls well below.

Figure 6 compares the three candidate formulations as a function of λ_{PD} . Formulation (A) incorrectly predicts that depeg risk *decreases* CVA, while Formulations (B) and (C) correctly capture the increasing effect. We note that (B) and (C) are *mathematically equivalent*—they differ only in how the total adjustment is decomposed, not in the resulting CVA value. We adopt (C) because its additive SCVA term provides a named, independently reportable quantity that mirrors the role of CCA in the Fujii–Takahashi framework.

Figure 6: CVA differential under three formulations. (A) is mathematically distinct; (B) and (C) are equivalent but differ in decomposition. We adopt (C) for its additive SCVA structure.

Figure 7 visualizes the ΔCVA decomposition under USDC baseline parameters.

Figure 7: ΔCVA decomposition. Settlement reduction (-0.000329) vs. SCVA ($+0.000694$). Net $\Delta\text{CVA} = +0.000365$.

4 Conclusion

4.1 Summary of Contributions

This paper makes three contributions. (i) We propose a separation-type decomposition of the CVA for stablecoin-denominated atomic settlement into a conventional CVA term and a new additive adjustment, the **Settlement Currency Valuation Adjustment (SCVA)**, conceptually corresponding to the Collateral Cost Adjustment (CCA) of [Fujii and Takahashi](#)

(2013). (ii) Under a two-state Markov depeg model, we derive a semi-analytical closed-form expression for SCVA (Eq. (8)) and validate it against a 100,000-path Monte Carlo simulation, with relative error below 0.32%. (iii) Under USDC 2023 parameters, SCVA exceeds the settlement-period CVA reduction by a factor of approximately 2.1. The commonly cited atomic-settlement benefit—elimination of settlement-period counterparty risk—can be offset by settlement-currency depeg risk unless issuer soundness is sufficiently secured.

4.2 Policy Implications

Regulators designing frameworks for stablecoin-denominated securities settlement should consider SCVA as a quantitative criterion for stablecoin eligibility. The breakeven condition $\delta \cdot \lambda_{PD} \approx 0.0113$ provides a principled threshold: stablecoins with depeg parameters above this curve *increase* systemic counterparty risk rather than reduce it. The cross-stablecoin analysis demonstrates this concretely: a Type II Fund Transfer Business stablecoin under the revised Japanese Payment Services Act (with trust-based 101%+ bankruptcy-remote custody and par redemption rights, e.g., Article 43) achieves near-zero SCVA, enabling the full CVA benefit of atomic settlement. By contrast, prepaid-type tokens from the same issuer—lacking redemption rights and traded on DeFi markets—exhibit SCVA at $4.4\times$ the settlement reduction. The **legal form** of the stablecoin—specifically, whether par redemption is guaranteed and reserves are held in legally bankruptcy-remote trust assets—is decisive.

4.3 Limitations

(i) The two-state Markov model is a deliberate simplification; actual depeg dynamics may exhibit jump-diffusion or state-dependent transition rates.

(ii) Our specification treats SCVA as independent of counterparty credit risk. In reality, depeg events are often triggered by systemic stress (e.g., the SVB crisis) that simultaneously elevates default probabilities—a textbook **Wrong-Way Risk (WWR)** structure (Brigo et al., 2018). As an illustrative quantification, assuming a Gaussian copula driven by a common systemic factor with correlation $\rho = 0.3$ yields a conditional depeg probability $\Pr(D_t | \text{default}_t) \approx \pi_D(t) + \rho \cdot \sigma_{\text{stress}}$ that inflates SCVA by approximately $1.3\text{--}1.5\times$. Under USDC baseline parameters, this corresponds to $\text{SCVA} \approx 0.0009\text{--}0.0010$ and a settlement-reduction ratio of approximately $2.7\text{--}3.1$. The independent specification thus represents a **lower bound** on true depeg-adjusted CVA.

(iii) The analysis is restricted to the CVA dimension of settlement risk. Atomic settlement offers additional benefits—elimination of Herstatt risk, reduced operational risk, improved capital efficiency (Auer et al., 2022; Bank for International Settlements, 2023)—outside the present scope.

(iv) The settlement-period CVA uses a conservative peak-exposure approximation ($EE_{\text{settle}} = 0.1 \cdot EE_0$). A more refined treatment along the lines of Brigo et al. (2013, Ch. 5) would alter the absolute value, but the qualitative dominance of SCVA over the settlement reduction is robust for $EE_{\text{settle}}/EE_0 \in [0.05, 0.20]$.

(v) Calibration relies on a small sample of historical depeg events. While the cross-sectional analysis across multiple stablecoins (USDC 2023, USDT 2022, UST 2022, DAI 2023) improves

robustness, formal panel calibration with statistically founded $(\delta, \lambda_{PD}, \lambda_{DP})$ estimates is left to subsequent work.

4.4 Future Research

Natural extensions include: (i) generalization of the depeg dynamics to a Merton jump-diffusion process and panel calibration across multiple stablecoins; (ii) rigorous derivation of WWR-adjusted SCVA within the FBSDE framework of [Fujii and Takahashi \(2013\)](#), via Gâteaux differentiation with explicit common-factor coupling between depeg intensity and hazard rate; (iii) a mean-field-game extension along the lines of [Fujii and Takahashi \(2022\)](#), where market participants' CVA-management actions feed back into aggregate depeg risk, providing a natural bridge to the equilibrium-pricing literature.

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A Parameter Specification

The exposure profile $EE(t) = EE_0 \cdot \sqrt{t} \cdot e^{-\alpha t}$ with $EE_0 = 100$, $\alpha = 0.15$ approximates the expected positive exposure of a 10-year interest rate swap portfolio with normalized notional. In a production implementation, $EE(t)$ would be generated from a Hull–White or G2++ model calibrated to the JGB yield curve, via Monte Carlo simulation with variance reduction.

The default density $q(t) = h \cdot e^{-ht}$ with $h = 0.01/\text{year}$ corresponds to an investment-grade counterparty (approximately BBB-rated). The recovery rate $R = 0.40$ follows Basel regulatory standards.

The settlement-period CVA component for Scenario A is computed as $\text{CVA}_{\text{settle}} = (1 - R) \cdot EE_{\text{settle}} \cdot (1 - e^{-h\Delta})$, where $\Delta = 2/365$ is the T+2 settlement period and $EE_{\text{settle}} = 0.10 \cdot EE_0$ is a conservative peak-exposure proxy during the settlement window. A more refined dynamic treatment (cf. [Brigo et al., 2013](#), Ch. 5) would alter the absolute level but not the SCVA/settle ratio, which is robust for $EE_{\text{settle}}/EE_0 \in [0.05, 0.20]$ (see §4.3).

The Poisson 95% confidence interval for λ_{PD} is computed using the exact method: for $k = 1$ observed events in $T_{\text{obs}} = 5$ years, the interval is $[\chi_{0.025}^2(2k)/(2T_{\text{obs}}), \chi_{0.975}^2(2k + 2)/(2T_{\text{obs}})] = [0.005, 1.114]/\text{year}$.

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